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SECURITY AND PRIVACY OF SMART CITY: IDEOLOGY, TECHNOLOGIES AND
FUNCTIONALITY OF THE SECURITY SYSTEM

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Annotation. *With recent advances of information and communication technology, smart city has been emerged as a new paradigm to dynamically optimize the resources in cities and provide better facilities and quality of life for the citizens. Smart cities involve a variety of components, including ubiquitous sensing devices, heterogeneous networks, large-scale databases, and powerful data centers to collect, transfer, store, and intelligently process real-time information. Smart cities can offer new applications and services for augmenting the daily life of citizens on making decisions, energy consumption, transportation, healthcare, and education. It also presents a thematic taxonomy of security and privacy issues of smart cities to highlight the security requirements for designing a secure smart city, identify the existing security and privacy solutions, and present open research issues and challenges of security and privacy in smart cities.*

Keywords: *Smart cities, security, privacy, Internet of Things, cloud computing, big data, smart city, smart economy, information and communication technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

When it comes to the security system of large infrastructure facilities, in particular "smart cities", the question inevitably arises of a general, conceptual approach to its construction, to which the customer will have to find an answer and, in accordance with it, choose a system that meets his requirements.

In the process of assessing all the factors that are significant for building a protection complex and selecting the optimal solution, the customer will have to comprehensively comprehend the organizational, technological and functional components of the approach to the security system of an infrastructure facility. These include cities.

Consider which component is usually the most significant for the customer and why. Let's try to figure out what, in principle, are the three aspects of the approach to the security system.

Currently, the world's population is more than 7.5 billion people, of which almost half - 3.7 billion - live in cities, while 10 years ago the share of the urban population was 35-40%. To solve the problems of overloading transport communications, emergency rescue and municipal services of cities and serving the rapidly growing population of cities in the world, the concept of "Smart City" (Smart City) is becoming more widespread. City , E - City) [1–4].

A city is a system that has complex interdependent relationships within itself, which includes both the population living in it and the dynamic production of everything necessary for a person [2]. "Smart City" or " Smart city " - is a modern concept of integrating information and communication technologies for city property management. The main goal of creating a "smart

city" is to improve the quality of life of the population using urban informatics technology to improve service efficiency and meet the needs of residents based on three types of basic networks: communications, the Internet and the "Internet of Things" (Internet of Things , IoT) [3]. This technology allows city authorities to interact directly with communities and urban infrastructure, monitor what is happening in the city and the development of the urban environment, and also find new ways to improve the quality of life. Through the use of sensors integrated in real time, the accumulated data from urban residents and various devices is processed and analyzed.

Cisco defines a "smart city" as a city that uses digital technologies or information and communication technologies (connected via a smart grid) to find optimal solutions to the problems of various areas of urban life. These areas may include parking, traffic, transportation, street lighting, water and waste management, security, even the delivery of education and health services. A smart city is based on technological solutions that optimize the support and delivery of urban services, reduce resource consumption and keep prices down. In the world there are a large number of examples of the introduction of various "smart" technologies in the life of cities. Thus, Barcelona (Spain) pays great attention to the protection and protection of the environment. Copenhagen (Denmark) - specializes in saving energy through various events, initiatives and actions with the active participation of city residents. Vancouver (Canada) is the center of the clean technology industry. Montreal (Canada) - a single card has been developed for using public transport, as in Moscow. In San Francisco (USA), a special application helps smartphone users to search for free parking spaces throughout the city. Elements of the "smart city" system To the basic subsystems " Smart City » 6 elements can be attributed:

- intelligent transport system
- geoinformation system
- electronic police
- safety
- e-education
- e-health

The Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) optimizes traffic by displaying the traffic situation on street information panels and smartphones of users, prompts them for the best route, controls the operation of traffic lights depending on the workload of intersections, shows the place and time of arrival at a public transport stop, the estimated time spent on road and many other useful features.

IDEOLOGY OF THE SYSTEM

The organizational component is directly related to the general ideology that a company operating in the security market adheres to. And the ideology of the organization greatly influences the choice of the concept of the security system. These are the dependent factors. There are two key decisions here:

1. the use of systems consisting of disparate, unrelated elements, for example, video surveillance systems and access control systems;
2. construction of an integrated security system.

System of individual "cubes". There is an opinion that disparate systems, such as fire alarms, perimeter security and video surveillance, which are not integrated with each other, are

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easier to maintain and more reliable. After all, the more complex the system, the more qualified personnel are required to maintain it. A system assembled from separate "cubes" requires less qualified personnel.

This opinion is often heard. In addition, such an approach is often forced to be used in large-scale infrastructure projects such as "Safe City", in cases where funding is provided by different departments and sources - for example, through the traffic police, housing and communal services, etc. – and each of these customers implements its own system. Accordingly, different structures are responsible for the result. At the same time, there is often not enough administrative resource to consolidate all interested departments in advance to fulfill a common task and think over the concept of building an integrated security system at a distributed facility. Often there is a situation when two departmental services build their own security systems at the same facility, which completely duplicate each other. Up to the fact that two cameras are installed in the same place, aimed at the same point and belonging to two different departments - and all this is only due to administrative separation and insufficient coordination of actions. It turns out, one object and double costs!

Distributed Platform System. We fully share the idea that the optimal solution for large and complex facilities, including smart cities, is a distributed platform on which an integrated security system is built.

Such a system really requires qualified personnel. But, firstly, much fewer employees are needed to service it. Secondly, different departments will receive the same information, and the quality of this information will be noticeably higher. Thirdly, the same infrastructure will be used for collecting, transmitting, storing information and maintaining the security system, which will reduce costs, this is very significant, especially for large-scale projects, the implementation costs of which are high anyway.

Data center in a smart city. It is important to remember that, in addition to the network infrastructure - the transport that delivers information to the recipients - there is a physical infrastructure, such as data processing centers (DPCs).

What is a DPC? It's not just desktops, monitors, storage servers, and video walls . This is a building, people, engineering systems, electricity. The construction and maintenance of this entire economy requires huge funds. However, if you implement an integrated, distributed security system as part of the Smart City project, one data center will supply information to many interested departments and services - from housing and communal services to law enforcement agencies and even federal level structures.

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Picture 1. Exploiting data centers energy flexibility in smart cities.

In addition, there is a certain specificity associated with the so-called information impenetrability of some departments that seek to accumulate important data exclusively within the framework of structures accountable only to them. However, the security system and the data center in this case act not as a consumer, but as a content accumulator, as a router that distributes information flows between interested services, maintains the system, and maintains the infrastructure in working order. That is, this is a service provider, not a consumer, so information is transmitted to departments exclusively "from outside to inside".

In general, the coverage area of a safe city can be divided into three large clusters:

1. video security and safety of the urban environment, including roads, provided by law enforcement agencies;
2. management of housing and communal services;
3. protection of strategic facilities.

In terms of technical approaches to the security system of large infrastructure facilities, in particular "smart cities", it is important that there are two fundamentally different areas between which a choice is made:

1. client-server or distributed architecture;
2. a solution from one manufacturer (mono-brand) or a single software open platform that can work with equipment from a variety of manufacturers.

Client-server or distributed architecture. If we talk about these two approaches in the context of "smart cities", then the same limitations and opportunities work here as when choosing an organizational approach. The client-server architecture implies a relative simplicity of the solution and fewer requirements for personnel. A distributed, complex, integrated system requires very high qualifications from employees, but at the same time provides much more opportunities and, with proper management and careful study at the concept stage, is much more effective. It is important to be flexible here: since we are dealing with a city - an object of unprecedented complexity - each part of the system must be approached individually. It is very important to remember that a distributed system can always be reduced to a client-server system if necessary, but it is impossible to expand a client-server system to a distributed one, since the client-server architecture is, in fact, a special case of a distributed architecture.

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Picture 2. Client server architecture in smart cities.

However, today the situation has changed dramatically, and this is due to the ultra-rapid development of security technologies. Every day there is something new, and there are no companies that, having created a super brand, can rest on their laurels. Companies that 20 years ago were winners and "ruled" the market are now forced to change, trying to offer something innovative and, in fact, returning to the start-up stage. The reason for this is the IP revolution in the security market, which quickly changed both the balance of power and development vectors.

The IP market is growing rapidly, video analytics tools are actively developing, there are no industry standards, and therefore it is not clear what the balance of power will be in it. The company that is more innovative and responsive to customer needs will be the winner.

Picture 3. Distributed architecture in a smart city

Today, a modern security system must meet the highest criteria of the IT industry and be at the forefront of technology. But it is obvious that one company cannot develop all the components of the system, equipping them exclusively with innovative and most advanced tools. A task of this level can be solved only by combining the efforts and knowledge of the best of the best so that the synergy effect works.

CONCLUSION

Today, everything has changed thanks to the rapid development of video analysis technologies. Thus, there are already unique non-relativistic databases for indexing and storing a

description of what is happening in the space captured by a video camera, which allows, together with the video, to record in the archive the characteristics of all objects moving in the frame - metadata - and then perform a quick search for video recordings in the archive using these characteristics. Video is a completely different matter, here there were no adequate ways to index and save information until recently. Therefore, customers tend to choose security systems based on a distributed architecture, as they provide more room for change and improvement of the complex protection of the object.

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